

STRUCTURATION OF ADHESION PROMOTERS AT INTERFACES: A MOLECULAR LEVEL INVESTIGATION

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1 General Introduction

The modification of metal surfaces with organic monolayers and thin films is a vast subject that impacts upon a wide variety of technologically and scientifically important areas. Such monolayers, often referred to as self-assembled monolayers (SAMs), are used in fields such as catalysis, corrosion protection studies, lubrication, adhesion, chemical sensors, biological applications (as platforms for the studies of protein adsorption and cell adhesion due to their simplicity and flexibility), control of the wetting properties, lithographical applications and molecular electronics.

Adhesion promoters are dedicated organic molecules used in composite industries to improve stress transfer between organic polymer matrix and the reinforcing element. The process of spontaneous adsorption and organization of adhesion promoters from dilute solution has been successfully employed previously with a number of long chain molecules at metal surfaces and the method offers a simple and attractive method for surface modification at the single monolayer level [1-2].

Adhesion promoters are usually prepared by immersion of solid substrates in solutions containing reactants that spontaneously adsorb on the surface and form an ordered structure. They are thus particularly attractive in designing and controlling the surface properties [3]. The ordered final structure results from the combination of three factors: the anchorage on the substrate surface, the Van der Waals lateral interactions between the aliphatic parts of the molecules (self-assembling), and the nature of interactions between the terminal functional groups.

An understanding of the mechanisms governing the growth and structure of this thin organic layer [4] is a major step forward for optimal performance of the resulting composite material. This study focuses on the properties of coupling agents (i.e. adhesion promoters) on various substrates. The study of the structuration of these ultra-thin layers is based on a multi-technique and multi-scale approach. On the basis of surface advanced spectroscopic and microscopic techniques, the present study contribute to understanding the mechanisms that govern adsorption, growth, structuration of coupling agent ultra-thin layers on inorganic substrates [5]. All results presented in this work demonstrate the interest of multi-techniques and multi-scales approach in the characterization of ultra-thin organic films.

2 Experimental

2.1 Grafting conditions

The substrates for grafting are glass plates covered by gold, aluminium, copper, or zinc, which have suffered several cleaning treatments before direct contact with the thiol, amine or silane molecules. Indeed, a monolayer of 3-mercaptopropyltriethoxy silane is grafted on glass plates previously cleaned. This layer coupling agent provides a good deposit of the metal layer having a thickness of 120 nm. This thickness is optimal in terms of surface reflectivity and well adapted to the various spectroscopic techniques of analysis. After metallic deposition, the grafting is done by immersing the substrate in a solution of coupling agent molecules in ethanol.

Thiol, amine and silane based coupling agent molecules are purchased from Aldrich and were adsorbed from solution onto the different substrates (Au, Al, Cu, Zn). The grafting is done by immersing

the substrate in a solution of adhesion promoters (thiols, amines or silanes) in ethanol.

A wide number of coupling agent molecules were studied, having different head a tail groups as well as different chain length. Nevertheless, the results obtained on only few of them will be given in the present paper.

These are for amine anchoring group the hexadecylamine, for HS anchoring group the hexadecanethiol, 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid, methyl-11-mercaptoundecanoate, aminothiophenol and for silane anchoring group the hexadecyltrichlorosilane, 1H,1H,2H,2H perfluoro decylmethylchlorosilane, (6-aminoethyl)-amino propyltrimethoxysilane and 2(carbomethoxy) ethyltrichlorosilane.

2.2 Techniques for interface characterization

A variety of analytical techniques were used to characterize the different substrates and interface formed through adhesion promoters grafting. The characterization techniques used for this study were: wettability to access surface energy of the substrates before and after grafting, atomic force microscopy (AFM) to characterize the morphology of the organic thin layer formed, and polarization modulation infrared spectroscopy in reflection mode (PM-IRRAS) to access the molecular orientation of the adsorbed molecules [6]. Ellipsometry also helps us to determine, in some cases the thickness of the adsorbed layer.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 AFM results

Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) in tapping mode is a technique used in our study in order to extract information on the adsorption substrates, on the organization of functional molecules present at the grafted substrates surface and to obtain quantitative measurements of some parameters such as size and organization of identified structures.

Figure 1 shows characteristic AFM images in tapping mode of the some of the metallic substrates, namely gold, copper and zinc.

Fig. 1: AFM (tapping mode) images of gold (a), copper (b) and zinc (c) substrates.

For gold substrate it can be observed a characteristic organization of gold atoms into substantially spherical islets with a size of about 30 nm to 40 nm. The phase contrast image is the most interesting because it reveals in particular intergranular contrasts. The average roughness is equal to 1.2 nm.

In the case of the copper substrate, the morphology is similar to the gold substrate, but with a larger size of islets about 60 nm resulting in a higher roughness equal to 1.4 nm.

The phase contrast images of the zinc substrate after metallization show a characteristic organization of zinc atoms in platelet aggregates of mean size 150 nm. Roughness is then rather high (54 nm) that will make difficult further analysis by polarization modulation infrared spectroscopy in reflection mode (PM-IRRAS) to access the molecular orientation of the adsorbed molecules.

Just after immersion in the solution of coupling agents (thiols, amines or silanes), homogeneous

deposit is observed, as well as an island structure of individual average size equal to 30 nm. This size does not depend on the nature of the substrate. However intermediate structures have been observed for short immersion time. They seem to depend on the nature and morphology of the substrate. For optimum immersion time, there would be stabilization alkyl chains by lateral van der Waals interactions leading to a restructuring of the alkyl chains in stable nanodomains of characteristic size 30 nm, regardless of the substrate.

3.2 Thickness of the adhesion promoter layer

The adsorption leads to the achievement of dense monolayers and compact in most cases. The difference in thickness, depending on the adhesion promoter / substrate under investigation can be explained in two ways: a difference of conformation and therefore a difference of alkyl chains tilt angle from the normal to the substrate, or by a different covering density. As an example Table 1 gathers the thickness values of coupling agent layers formed after adsorption and measured on different substrates, and thus for two types of molecules, namely amine and thiol based molecules.

Coupling agent	Substrate	Thickness(Å)
1--hexadecanethiol	Gold	19
	Copper	16
	Zinc	11
1- hexadecylamine	Gold	12
	Copper	10
	Zinc	3

Table 1: Thicknesses of amine and thiol based coupling agent layers after adsorption on different substrates.

One can see that on rather smooth substrate (Au, Cu) for which the average surface roughness is smaller than the coupling agent molecule extended length, these latter form dense and compact monolayer the thickness of which is close to the size of the

coupling agent molecule. On the contrary, on rough substrate (Zn), adsorption and grafting is less efficient leading to a low surface covering and probably to an heterogeneous grafted surface. For this reason we will further focus on the adsorption and structuration of coupling agent molecules on gold or copper substrates.

3.3 PM-IRRAS analysis of ultrathin films

The PM-IRRAS technique, known for its adaptability to analyze ultra thin films on metallic substrates, was employed to check both the chemisorption and the anisotropy of thiols on the gold surface. By applying the reflection-absorption selection rules one can access the orientation state of the coupling agent molecule as well as the associated angle value: changes in bands intensity relative to the bulk (considered as the isotropic state) are relevant to preferential orientation and anisotropy.

The basis and the principles of this technique were extensively described in our previous works [7-8] and can be summarised as: an intensification of an IR band is observed when the corresponding transition dipole moment is orientated parallel to the substrate normal.

All spectra were done with a PMA 50 PM-IRRAS Modulus (Bruker Optics) and all spectra were recorded with a MCT detector under experimental conditions of 2000 scans, resolution of 2 cm⁻¹ and 85° as beam incidence angle. A ZnSe photoelastic modulator provided by HINDS was used and IR beam polarization plane modulation frequency was set to 100 kHz. It is important to note that all the PM-IRRAS spectra have been scaled in order to present them together with the transmission spectra, thus making the comparison easier.

3.4 Kinetic of adsorption and surface covering

During grafting of coupling agent molecules on metallic substrates, the monolayer formation is defined by a simplified two-step process:

- (1) A fast process characterized by the evolution of surface coverage versus time. The amount of grafted

molecules increases until a fully covered surface is obtained. The kinetics of this step depends on the solution concentration, the temperature and the nature of the adhesion promoter.

(2) A slower process during which grafted molecules reorganize in well-packed structures. This self-assembling depends on the chemical with the substrate and physical interactions between grafts, which greatly affect the adsorption (covalent bonding), the orientation and the packing density of the surface species. It is of major importance to note that self-assembling begins before total coverage of the surface is obtained, as shown in Fig. 2. According to the literature this step could take hours.

Fig. 2: Surface coverage (τ) versus grafting reaction time.

At the end of the second step, the modified surface is covered by organized monomolecular assemblies that arise as a compromise between many parameters, such as covalent bonding and intermolecular interactions between adjacent adsorbed adhesion promoter molecules.

According to Fig. 2, points A, B and C do not present the same grafted surface and could be defined according to the surface coverage (τ) and assembly organization:

- (1) $A(t_1, \tau_1)$: partially covered surface ($\tau_1 < 1$) obtained after a period τ_1 of grafting reaction.
- (2) $B(t_2, \tau_2)$: fully covered surface ($\tau_2 = 1$) but incomplete structural organization of grafted species (time t_2).
- (3) $C(t_3, \tau_3)$: fully covered surface with stable structured assemblies packed in the monomolecular

film of thiol molecules. Thus, on the basis of many works, we consider that for 3 mM solutions a grafting time of 12 h leads to fully covered surfaces.

Experimentally, we will illustrate this kinetic of adsorption for the aminothiophenol adhesion promoter [9]. Atomic force microscopy was used to image surfaces prepared by varying the grafting reaction time. Atomic force microscopy images in tapping mode of gold substrates after recorded at different grafting times show (Fig. 3) relevant differences for times 25, 90 and 180 min.

Fig. 3: AFM topographic images (5 μm x 5 μm) of N_{25} , N_{90} and N_{180} surfaces (z range = 20 nm).

This topographic comparison of NH_2 -modified substrates is very significant in terms of monomolecular film formation (all modified substrate topographic images were acquired with a vertical range of 20 nm).

The surface evolution does not show packed structures after 25 min. Such packed organizations became detectable (300 nm) only after 90 min of

grafting. Furthermore, surfaces prepared at 180 min (and more) were covered by stable thiol-packed islands (650 nm). We should mention that island diameters were measured directly by AFM. Calculated values represent an average of three measurements (uncertainty was 30 nm)

We would consider that measurements done at 25, 90 and 180 minutes correspond to different coverage–organization evolutions. On the other hand, these substrates were analyzed by PM-IRRAS technique and significant differences were observed between samples, for instance after 90 and 180 adsorption times (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4: PM-IRRAS spectra of N_{90} and N_{180} aminothiophenol gold grafted surfaces. Grafting times were respectively 90 and 180 minutes.

Two spectral zones are of particular interest. First the $3100 - 3600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ absorption domain which corresponds to NH_2 stretching mode and attributed to intermolecular hydrogen bonds between NH_2 functional groups, and second, the $1550 - 1700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ absorption domain which is relative to NH deformation mode of NH links. Comparing these spectra and taking into account the PM-IRRAS selection rules, we can deduce that band intensity changes are related to the orientational evolution of the NH_2 grafts. More precisely, the NH_2 band, which is relatively strong for 90 min. adsorption time, is not present on the 180 min. spectrum. Thus, we conclude that after 180 min. of reaction, the NH_2 grafts reorient in the plane of the surface, whereas they were almost perpendicular to the substrate after 90 min. (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1: Schematic representation of NH_2 grafts reorientation at two different grafting times (N_{90} and N_{180}).

3.5 Structuration of adhesion promoters at interfaces

The study of the molecular conformation of adhesion promoters adsorbed on inorganic substrates was made by the analysis of the FTIR spectral responses of adhesion promoter thin films using PM-IRRAS spectroscopy. Great numbers of molecules were adsorbed and their structuration were systematically investigated. Nevertheless, detailed results will be given hereafter only for a few of them in order to focus on the methodology we used.

3.5.1 Structuration of 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid

11-mercaptoundecanoic acid [$\text{HS}-(\text{CH}_2)_{10}-\text{COOH}$] adhesion promoter was grafted by immersion of the gold substrates for times ranging between 1 hour and 15 hours in a 3 mM solution of the acid in methanol. After this adsorption procedure, the grafted substrates were systematically washed to remove ungrafted molecules.

The PM-IRRAS technique allows checking both the chemisorption and the anisotropy of thiols on the gold surface. The access to a detailed description of the adsorbed layer of the 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid on the gold surface by PM-IRRAS can be

achieved by comparing the PM-IRRAS spectrum of the grafted surface with the bulk transmission spectrum (considered as the isotropic signal) of the adhesion promoter molecule considered, as shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5: Comparison of a) the bulk transmission spectrum of 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid and b) PM-IRRAS spectrum of the gold surface after acid grafting (immersion time = 3 hrs)

Details of the attribution and the position of the acid main infrared bands are presented in Table 2.

Position (cm ⁻¹)	Vibrational mode	Abbreviation
2920	Asymmetric CH ₂ stretching	ν _{as} (CH ₂)
2849	Symmetric CH ₂ stretching	ν _s (CH ₂)
2565 (very weak)	S-H stretching	ν(SH)
1712	Carbonyl stretching	ν(C=O)
1590	Carbonyl stretching (H-Bonds)	ν(C=O)
1400-1471	CH ₂ scissoring	δ _s (CH ₂)
1190	OC-O stretching	ν(OC-O)

Table 2: Characteristic infrared vibration modes of 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid

Firstly, Figure 5 shows that the acid characteristic main bands are present in the PM-IRRAS spectrum of the grafted surface indicating that the chemisorption of the 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid occurs with an optimal grafting density. Indeed, spectra recorded over an immersion time period ranging from 1 hour to 15 hours show that for immersion time of 3 hours or more, the formation of

a closely packed monolayer is achieved. The 1590 cm⁻¹ vibration mode is assigned to the carbonyl stretching mode of carboxylic acid groups involved in strong acid-base interactions (H-Bonds) induced by lateral packing of the thiol molecules after adsorption and self-assembling. Even if not used for quantitative calculation of the alkyl chain orientation angle, the presence of this band demonstrates the self-organization and strong packing of acid ended thiol molecules.

Moreover, as mentioned before, changes in bands intensities between the bulk and the thin layer are typically due to molecular anisotropy. To study the orientation of acid SAMs, the evolutions of four main vibration modes were more precisely analyzed: ν_{as}(CH₂), ν_s(CH₂), ν(C=O), and ν(OC-O):

- The ν_s(CH₂) band intensity in the PM-IRRAS spectrum decreases relatively to the ν_{as}(CH₂) one when comparing with the bulk signal. Such a variation indicates that the ν_s(CH₂) transition dipole moment is more parallel to the surface than the ν_{as}(CH₂) one (selection rules).
- The ν(C=O) band intensity around 1712 cm⁻¹ decreases in the PM-IRRAS spectrum (compared to the bulk) indicating a quasi-parallel orientation of its transition dipole moment with respect to the substrate plane.
- The ν(OC-O) band intensity (at 1190 cm⁻¹) is comparable in the PM-IRRAS and transmission spectra.

It can be deduced that the parallel orientation of the ν_s(CH₂) and ν(C=O) transition dipole moments could only be possible if the molecule main axis and plane are quasi-perpendicular to the surface plane. 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid is grafted with a slight tilt with respect to the substrate normal which is the typical anisotropy for self-assembled monolayer.

For an exact representation of the global geometry, two main angles should be considered:

- φ : the tilt angle with respect to the substrate normal.
- α : the angle separating the main chain axis and the normal in the chain plane

The calculation of these angles is needed to confirm the qualitative interpretation of PM-IRRAS spectrum. For such a calculation it is known that in PM-IRRAS, the band intensity of a vibration mode is related to the bulk one (transmission) via a geometrical function F defined by the orientation of the corresponding transition dipole moment:

$$I_i \propto [F_i(\varphi, \alpha \dots)]^2 \cdot A_i$$

Where I_i is the PM-IRRAS experimental integrated intensity of a given band, and A_i is the bulk isotropic state integrated intensity (these two parameters are experimentally obtained).

After the determination of F for the chosen bands, the calculated values of α (31°) and φ (32°) are in excellent agreement with a quasi-perpendicular orientation of the 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid on the gold surface and are consistent with those mentioned in the literature. Indeed, the results obtained highlight the importance of hydrogen bonds that promote the formation of a compact monolayer in which the molecules are oriented almost in the normal direction with respect to the substrate plane.

3.5.2 Structuration of methyl-11-mercaptoundecanoate

What will happen when the end functionality of the thiol adhesion promoter changes from acid to ester ?

Significant differences were observed between the bulk transmission FTIR spectrum and the PM-IRRAS spectrum of the adsorbed monolayer (Fig. 6). The study of the molecular conformation of thiol-ester adhesion promoters adsorbed on gold substrate was made by the analysis of spectral responses of methylene functional groups of the alkyl chains, absorbing in the wavelengths $2800\text{-}3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ interval. Comparison shows that there is indeed alkyl chains conformational anisotropy.

Two main points can be discussed according to Figure 6:

- The characteristic vibration modes of the ester are present on the PM-IRRAS spectrum indicating that the adsorption occurred on the gold surface.

Fig. 6: Comparison of a) the bulk transmission spectrum of methyl-11-mercaptoundecanoate and b) PM-IRRAS spectrum of the gold surface after thiol-ester grafting.

- On the PM-IRRAS spectrum, $\nu_s(\text{CH}_2)$ and $\nu_{as}(\text{CH}_2)$ bands preserve almost the same intensity ratio as in the bulk while the $\nu_{as}(\text{CH}_3)$ band becomes very intense compared to all the other one. On the other hand the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ band remains very intense compared to the $\nu_s(\text{CH}_2)$ and $\nu_{as}(\text{CH}_2)$ bands.

These changes are possible only if the main plane and axis of the molecule are more parallel than perpendicular with respect to the gold substrate. According to this representation $\nu_s(\text{CH}_2)$ and $\nu_{as}(\text{CH}_2)$ transition dipole moments are both in an intermediate position between parallel and perpendicular with respect to the gold surface while the $\nu_{as}(\text{CH}_3)$ transition dipole moment is almost perpendicular and thus justifying the high intensity of its band on the PM-IRRAS spectrum.

The calculated values of the orientation angles for the thiol-ester grafts are $\alpha = 52^\circ$ and $\varphi = 54^\circ$. According to these results, when grafting the methyl-11-mercaptoundecanoate on the gold surface, it can be deduced that the formation of anisotropic monolayer with a rather flattened orientation with respect to the substrate plane is obtained, thus leading to a low grafting density. This ester adsorption geometry is justified by the absence of high energy of interactions such as hydrogen bonds between the ester terminal functionalities.

Steric hindrance of ester end group do not allow alkyl chain packing through van der Waals interactions as one could suspect.

3.6 Influence of substrate on structuration

The study of the molecular conformation of 1-hexadecanethiol and 1-hexadecylamine adsorbed on metallic substrates was made by the analysis of spectral responses of the most intense vibrators located in the wavelengths 2800-3000 cm^{-1} interval. Significant differences were observed between the bulk spectrum and PM-IRRAS spectra of adsorbed monolayers. The calculation of the orientation angles of the grafted molecules relative to the normal to the substrate surface (determined using the selection rules specific to the PM-IRRAS spectroscopy) show that the alkyl chains are organized during the adsorption. They are in trans-trans conformations and exhibit a tilt angle from the normal to the plane of the interface ranging between 19° to 39° depending on the nature of the inorganic substrate. Broadly speaking, the tilt direction of alkyl chain depends on the nature of the, but depends mainly on the nature of the anchoring group (thiol or amine in the present case) functionalities. The lateral van der Waals inter-chains forces determine the orientation of chains within the layer.

Moreover, the results obtained showed that alkanethiols establish chemical bonds at the interface with a large variety of inorganic substrates or metallic substrates. In the case adsorbed alkylamine on metallic substrates, the presence of amine (NH_2) and protonated amine (NH_3^+) is demonstrated for unoxidized substrates. On oxidized ones a covalent grafting is evidenced.

4 Conclusion

In this work, we were interested in the study of grafting of adhesion promoter molecules to highlight the formation of thin structured films, and characterize the organization of these grafted systems using techniques applied to the analysis of surfaces and interfaces (PM-IRRAS and AFM). The results obtained in this study showed that the great sensitivity of the PM-IRRAS technique, has permitted us to identify the effects of

molecular orientation within the layer which seem to depend on the nature of the substrate. In all cases structuration phenomenon occur leading to the formation of organized, homogeneous and compact monolayer. All results presented in this study demonstrate the interest of multi-techniques and multi-scales approaches in the characterization of ultra-thin organic layers.

References

- [1] Porter, M.D., Bright, T.B., Allara, D.L., Chidsey, C.E.D. "Spontaneously organized molecular assemblies. 4. Structural characterization of n-alkyl thiol monolayers on gold by optical ellipsometry, infrared spectroscopy, and electrochemistry", *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 109, 3559-3568 (1987)
- [2] Allara, D.L., Swalen, J.D. "An infrared reflection spectroscopy study of oriented cadmium arachidate monolayer films on evaporated silver", *J. Phys. Chem.* 86, 2700-2704 (1982)
- [3] Bain, C.D., Whitesides, G.M. "Molecular-Level Control over Surface Order in Self-Assembled Monolayer Films of Thiols on Gold", *Science*, 240, 62-63 (1988)
- [4] Elzein T., Brogly M. and Schultz J. "Adhesion : Current Research and Applications". Wiley-VCH, 2005
- [5] Elzein T., Fahs A., Brogly M., Elhiri A., Lepoittevin B., Roger P., Planchot V. "Adsorption of Alkanethiols on Gold Surfaces: PM-IRRAS Study of the Influence of Terminal Functionality on Alkyl Chain Orientation", *The Journal of Adhesion*, 89, 416-432 (2013)
- [6] Elzein T, Brogly M., Schultz J. "Quantitative calculation of the orientation angles of adsorbed polyamides nanofilms", *Polymer* 44, 3649-3660 (2003)
- [7] Elzein T, Brogly M., Schultz J. "Molecular orientation of EVA chains adsorbed on chemically controlled surfaces: influence of specific interactions", *Surf. Interface Anal.*, 35, 633-639 (2003)
- [8] Elzein T., Awada H., Nasser-Eddine M., Delaite C. and Brogly M. "A model of chain folding in Polycaprolactone-b-Polymethylmethacrylate diblock copolymers" *M. Thin Solid Films*, Vol. 483, pp 388-395, 2005
- [9] Elzein T, Brogly M., Schultz J. "Adsorption of polyamides on SAMs: effect of SAM grafting density on polyamide morphology", *Surf. Interface Anal.*, 35, 231-236 (2003)